

21GRD10 – quantiAGREMI

D1: Good Practice Guide on the developed traceable techniques for the quantification of NH₃ and CH₄ emissions from selected livestock housings for target applications (e.g., animal category, housing systems) with a target uncertainty of 10 % (CH₄) to 20 % (NH₃) for mechanically ventilated and 30 % (CH₄) to 40 % (NH₃) for naturally ventilated housing.

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1 Summary

The aim of the WP1 – Towards SI-traceable reference methods for livestock emissions factors – of the quantiAGREMI European project is to achieve SI-traceable quantification of NH_3 and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from livestock housings. Existing sophisticated techniques, such as the carbon dioxide (CO_2) balance or the external tracer ratio method to quantify relevant emissions from selected livestock housings, in particular for ammonia (NH_3) and methane (CH_4), will be improved and metrologically characterised. SI-traceability for the key-parameters of the selected techniques (especially amount fractions of target gases) will be established to assess their uncertainty. In the chapter 2 to 8 detailed input from A1.2.2 and A1.3.1 to A1.3.6 is provided by Empa, WBF-Agroscope, METAS, INRAE, PTB, VTT, CMI and TUBITAK.

The most critical parameters to reduce emission uncertainties towards 10 % (CH_4) and 20 % (NH_3) for mechanically ventilated, and 30 % (CH_4) and 40 % (NH_3) for naturally ventilated housing are summarized below:

- Reference gases:

Equivalence of NH_3 reference generators using different operation principles, dynamic dilution of gravimetric gas mixtures, permeation and liquid evaporation, was demonstrated (chapter 2). All reference gas generators provide good reproducibility (better than 0.8% in dry and wet air) and a good linearity on the measurement range from 0 to 400 $\text{nmol}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ in dry and wet air. The expanded uncertainties (0.023 to 0.031) on the slope of the regression line between the amount fractions of the generated gas mixtures and PTB spectroscopic measurement results are consistent for all gas generators and sufficient to reach the above uncertainty target specifications.

- Analytical techniques:

All tested commercial CRDS analysers for NH_3 , CO_2 and CH_4 show good linearity, small drift, often even better than manufacturer specifications sufficient to reach the above uncertainty target specifications (chapter 3).

Standard CRDS NH_3 analysers (Picarro Inc.) shows comparable performance to state-of-the-art CRDS analysers for measurements in a naturally ventilated dairy housing, sufficient to achieve the set uncertainty target specifications. In contrast, a standard Proceas CRDS could not resolve fluctuations of the NH_3 amount fraction, which might conflict with emissions quantification (chapter 7).

CRDS analysers are designed for target gas analysis in air – using it with N_2 may change signal noise and is known to lead to erroneous results, which might conflict with the above uncertainty target specifications (chapter 4).

CRDS, photoacoustic and FTIR spectroscopic devices provide superior data quality to low-cost sensors based on NDIR technology. Whether uncertainty target specifications can be reached with low-cost sensors upon calibration, has to be tested in the future (chapter 6).

- Tubing materials:

SilcoNert® coated stainless steel and PFA tubing is recommended over Dekabon tubing for applications focussing on small NH_3 concentrations changes, as it shows less time lags, which reduces measurement uncertainties (chapter 5).

- Novel tracer gases:

Ethan and ethine were evaluated as potential replacements for current tracer gases (e.g., SF_6) with lower environmental impact and the capability for on-line analytics at ambient concentrations. Commercial analytics for C_2H_6 / CH_4 (Aeris MIRA Ultra) demonstrated sufficient precision and accuracy when calibrated.

The reported findings are independent of the ventilation type (mechanically, naturally ventilated housing) and animal categories.

2 Equivalence of ammonia RGMs (A214; T. Macé, C. Sutour, LNE)

2.1 Objectives of the comparison

As part of the WP1 - Towards SI-traceable reference methods for livestock emissions factor of the European quantiAGREMI project, the task 1.2 aims to perform a comparison of dry and wet NH_3 reference gas mixtures (RGMs) at the $\text{nmol}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ (ppb) level in synthetic air, with four traceability chains: (1) dynamic dilution of gravimetric gas mixtures, (2) dynamic reference gas mixtures generated by the permeation method, (3) a laser based spectral method, and (4) dynamic reference gas mixtures generated using the evaporation method. Until now, there have been only two comparisons organized for dry NH_3 RGMs at much higher NH_3 amount fractions of about $30\ \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ and $14\ \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ (CCQM-K46 and CCQM-K117).

2.2 Brief description of the different reference generators

2.2.1 METAS

The reference generator provided by METAS called ReGaS3 is a transfer standard based on gas permeation and dynamic dilution. It can be used to generate reference gas mixtures with reactive components at atmospheric amount fractions, typically in the range between 2 and 2000 ppb. The core of the instrument is a temperature- and pressure-controlled oven with an adsorption resistant coating. It has 6 slots, 5 of which can hold a permeation tube, while the 6th contains a sensor to measure the temperature within the slot. An array of mass flow controllers (MFCs), mass flow meters (MFMs) and pressure controllers (PrCs) regulate the carrier gas flows and pressures.

The Hydra (also Controlled Evaporator Mixer, CEM) is a humidifier for reference gas mixtures. It can be used to humidify dry reference gases from 10 to 80% relative humidity at 20°C and ambient pressure (corresponding to a dew point between -12.6 and 16.4°C). Dry, clean carrier gas (generally nitrogen or synthetic air) and liquid water are injected to an evaporator with a temperature between 120 and 200°C . This humid air stream is then added to the dry reference gas flow and mixed in a tank before leaving the outlet. From the point where the humid and the dry reference gases are merged, all surfaces are Silconert@2000 coated, enabling humidification of reactive gas mixtures. The MFC of the carrier gas has a capacity of up to $4\ \text{L}/\text{min}$ STP (standard and temperature pressure) and is calibrated for nitrogen and synthetic air. The liquid flow controller can add 0.2 to $10\ \text{g}/\text{h}$ of water and is not calibrated.

The relative expanded uncertainty ($k=2$) on the generated NH_3 is around 1%.

2.2.2 LNE

The reference gas generator developed by LNE and 2MProcess is based on permeation method and consists of:

- a temperature-controlled oven at 30.00°C (to within 0.01°C) receiving the ammonia permeation tube from Fine Metrology, based in Italy and distributed by LNI,
- a first dilution stage consisting of two MFCs (id1 and id2) respectively of $120\ \text{ml}/\text{min}$ and $10\ \text{l}/\text{min}$ full scale to generate amount fractions between 400 and $60\ \text{nmol}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ (also depending on the permeation rate of the tube),
- a pressure regulator (1 bar relative) to regulate the gas pressure in the permeation oven,
- a second dilution stage consisting of two MFCs (id3 and id4) respectively of $120\ \text{ml}/\text{min}$ and $10\ \text{l}/\text{min}$ full scale to generate amount fractions between 50 and $1\ \text{nmol}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$.

All parts (tubing and MFCs) of this gas generator which are in contact with ammonia are SilcoNert2000® coated in order to limit as much as possible the adsorption of NH_3 on the walls. An integrated software (graphical interface) allows the automatic control of the MFCs and the calculation of the amount fraction of the generated dynamic gas mixture with its associated expanded uncertainty ($k=2$).

The relative expanded uncertainty ($k=2$) on the generated NH_3 in dry air is around 2.7%.

2.2.3 VSL

The dynamic dilution system for the generation of ammonia reference gas from VSL is based on the dilution using thermal mass flow controllers in two consecutive steps of gravimetrically prepared NH_3 standards. For the comparison an NH_3 reference mixture was prepared in 10 L AcuLife IV treated cylinder at 130 bars of pressure. The gas mixture was analysed at VSL both prior and after the comparison. For data analysis, the average determined amount fraction NH_3 was used ($102.43 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$).

The dynamic dilution system is based on two thermal MFCs in the first dilution stage to dilute the NH_3 reference mixture up to 400 times with air at a maximum flow rate of 4 L/min. An MFC was placed at the start of the second dilution stage to sample a portion of this reference gas and dilute it with dry air and with air that was humidified by passing through a wash bottle filled with milli-Q water. This allows to dilute the dynamically generated calibration gas another 800 times. A zero air from a 50 L cylinder was used in this comparison. All MFCs are of the type of EL Flow Prestige by Bronkhorst B.V. The pressure controllers are of the type of EL-PRESS by Bronkhorst B.V. and have an operating range of 2 bar(a). The software was developed at VSL in LabView® and allows control of the MFCs based on their calibration that was performed at VSL, registration of MFC performance and automatic generation of predefined gas mixtures.

The NH_3 gas mixture can be generated in dry or wet air with a relative expanded uncertainty ($k=2$) around 2.7%.

2.2.4 VTT

VTT's trace gas generator is based on liquid evaporation technique. It can be used for generating reference gases of water-soluble chemical compounds in a wide amount fraction range from $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ down to $\text{nmol}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ levels. It is especially well suited for compounds which easily stick to surfaces and for which it's challenging to produce traceable, long lived and stable static reference gas mixtures. It is also possible to make these systems portable, enabling their use both in laboratory and field conditions.

The operating principle is based on injecting a solution with known concentration into a carrier gas stream using an automatic syringe pump. Proper mixing and evaporation are ensured by applying a nozzle and evaporation heater. Synthetic air was used in this study as a carrier gas and the flow rate was controlled using a mass flow controller with a nominal flow range up of 10 L/min. A solution of ammonium hydroxide (NH_4OH) was used for generating low NH_3 amount fractions in air. Distilled water is used to flush the system between measurement runs.

The combination of all the sources of uncertainties components results leads to a relative expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$) of 1.9 % for all nominal amount fractions.

2.2.5 PTB

PTB used a Picarro G2103 spectrometer with a proprietary data evaluation method to achieve traceable, calibration-free NH_3 amount fraction measurements. The raw spectra were read out from the spectrometer and fitted by a separate software involving 8 NH_3 , 8 H_2O and 2 CO_2 spectral lines. Line intensities of the 3 strongest NH_3 lines, which are used for calculating the NH_3 amount fraction, have been measured at PTB using an independent laser spectroscopic set-up (Pogány *et al.*, 2021). Further spectral line parameters (air broadening coefficients, coefficients temperature dependence) have been taken from the HITRAN 2020 database (Gordon *et al.*, 2022). The built-in temperature and pressure sensors of the Picarro spectrometer have been compared to traceable temperature and pressure sensors at PTB to determine uncertainty of the temperature and pressure measurements.

To avoid sampling artefacts, the spectrometer is primarily being used in the laboratory for measuring gas mixtures not containing aerosols. The gas-sampling line contains two sub-micron Teflon filters, one connected to the gas inlet of the spectrometer, and being replaced by a new filter before each measurement campaign. The other filter is connected directly to the optical cavity and can only be replaced by the manufacturer. After occasional field measurements (last in 2016), the spectrometer is checked at PTB with known gas mixtures to ensure that no sampling artefacts are introduced due to contamination of the inner filter or the optical cavity. While measuring ambient air during the experiment at LNE, an additional filter was placed upstream of the spectrometer to protect the sampling line and filters of the spectrometer from aerosol contamination.

Expanded uncertainty of the calculated NH_3 amount fractions is around 3 % ($k = 2$) in the studied amount fraction range and is mainly determined by the uncertainty of the spectral fitting. Further important uncertainty

components, which have been taken into account are uncertainty of the spectral line parameters (primarily line intensities and air broadening coefficients of the 3 strongest NH_3 lines), as well as temperature and pressure of the gas sample in the optical cavity. Although the measurements have been performed under laboratory conditions and with sufficient stabilization time, uncertainty originating from gas sampling still has to be taken into account, especially at lower amount fractions. Influence of ambient temperature changes has been investigated in the range of 10-30 °C in a climate chamber and has been found negligible.

2.3 Precautions for the use of reference generators

2.3.1 Air supplied for dynamic NH_3 generation

VSL generator is supplied with a zero-air generator Teledyne (model T701) and with also air 6.0 in cylinder in order to generate NH_3 gas mixture at an amount fraction of 400 $\text{nmol}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ for 1 hour using a gaseous NH_3 reference material (VSL110738 cylinder).

Figure 1 highlights cyclical fluctuations of the zero-air generator. These fluctuations are not present when the dynamic system from VSL is supplied with synthetic air 6.0. This solution was chosen for the comparison while remaining vigilant with regard to consumption of synthetic air in order not to run out of air.

Figure 1: Generation of a gas mixture at 400 $\text{nmol}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ with VSL dynamic dilution using air compressor or air 6.0 in cylinder

2.3.2 Stability of NH_3 generated amount fraction

The NH_3 molecule is known to adsorb very easily on surfaces in contact with it. Most systems are therefore treated to limit this effect by a Silconert 2000 coating or use Teflon tubing. It is therefore important to evaluate the generation time required to obtain a stable response from the analyser which is a compromise between stability, air consumption and operating time.

Before generating NH_3 gas mixtures with VSL's generator, the pressure reducer of the cylinder is purged 5 times. For the ammonia generator based on permeation (METAS and LNE) and liquid evaporation (VTT), the stability of measurements is obtained in less than 2 hours.

Figure 2 indicates that even after 2 hours the stability of the measurements are not totally achieved for the VSL dilutor at 50 $\text{nmol}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$. The VSL dynamic dilution system is based on MFCs use and allows to automatically generate NH_3 gas mixtures; it is therefore possible to generate each level of NH_3 amount fractions for 3 hours to have a better stability.

In that way it takes 8 hours to achieve the generation of the four amount fractions levels during the comparison for METAS, LNE and VTT and 12 hours for VSL dynamic dilutor (automatic generation during the night). The negative peak of measurements observed for a VTT generator corresponding to the filling of the syringe.

For all ammonia generators, the stability of measurements is obtained in less than 2 hours.

Figure 2: Stability of the NH₃ measurements on PTB-Picarro reference analyser for the four reference generators from METAS, VSL, LNE and VTT at 50 nmol·mol⁻¹

Figure 3: Stability of the NH₃ measurements on PTB-Picarro reference analyser for the four reference generators from METAS, VSL, LNE and VTT at 400 nmol·mol⁻¹

2.4 Brief description of the comparison protocol

The different systems provided by LNE (with a flowrate up to 10 L/min), VSL (with a flowrate up to 8 L/min) and METAS (with a flowrate up to 10 L/min) generate **dry** dynamic reference gas mixtures at amount fractions of 0, 50, 200 and 400 nmol·mol⁻¹ NH₃ in synthetic air. PTB provides a laser-based reference device (Picarro spectrometer improved in JRP EMRP ENV55 MetNH3) also used as a standard.

The generation time of the different levels of NH₃ amount fractions was estimated at 2h for the manuals systems, which is a compromise between stability, gas consumption and working day and at 3h for the VSL system whose sequences can be programmed.

The experimental sequence of the Picarro-PTB calibration for dry NH₃ RGMs is the following: LNE-METAS-VSL-LNE-VSL-METAS-LNE-METAS-VSL-LNE.

The experimental sequence of the Picarro-PTB calibration for wet NH₃ RGMs is the following: METAS-VTT-VSL-METAS-VTT-METAS-METAS-VSL-VTT-VSL

2.5 Comparison results

For each day of NH₃ generation a linear regression of the spectroscopic measurement results (PTB) is evaluated using a GLS_GGMR method which allows to input the uncertainty on x and y. Using the software RegPoly developed by LNE (cf. Figure 4), the linear regression ($y = b_0 + b_1 \cdot x$) and slope (b1) are determined and its associated uncertainty.

Figure 4: RegPoly software developed by LNE

2.5.1 NH₃ comparison in dry air

A very good reproducibility on the determination of the average slopes of the linear regression of PTB analyser is observed for VSL and METAS generators with relative values lower than 0.2% in dry air. The reproducibility of LNE's generator is higher, i.e., around 0.8%, linked to a regulation problem of the permeation furnace which impacts on NH₃ amount fractions of the generated gas mixtures. This failure is now resolved. The consistency of the expanded uncertainty (k=2) of the average slopes between 0.023 and 0.031 can also be highlighted. Moreover, the figure 13 shows a good agreement between VSL and PTB, agreement between VSL and LNE and no agreement with METAS which over-estimated the NH₃ amount fractions.

Table 1: Average slopes and associated uncertainties of the linear regression of the spectroscopic measurement results (PTB) determined with the three NH₃ dynamic generators from METAS, VSL and LNE in dry air.

	Average slope	Reproducibility %	Expanded uncertainty (k=2)
METAS	1.108	0.07%	0.023
VSL	1.007	0.15%	0.024
LNE	1.041	0.75%	0.031

Figure 5: Representation of the average slope values of the PTB spectroscopic measurement results and associated uncertainty determined for the three NH₃ generators from METAS, VSL and LNE in dry air.

2.5.2 NH₃ comparison in wet air

A very good reproducibility on the determination of the average slopes of the linear regression of PTB spectroscopic measurements is observed for VSL and METAS generators with relative values lower than 0.5% and the reproducibility is equal to 0.72% for VTT in wet air; this reproducibility obtained for wet air is higher than those determined in dry air.

The consistency of the expanded uncertainty (k=2) of the average slopes between 0.025 and 0.026 can also be highlighted; it's similar than the results obtained for dry gas. Moreover, the figure 13 shows a good agreement between VSL and PTB, agreement between VSL and VTT and no agreement with METAS which over-estimated the amount fractions.

Table 2: Average slopes and associated uncertainties of the linear regression of the PTB spectroscopic measurements determined with the three NH₃ dynamic generators from METAS, VSL and VTT in wet air.

	Average slope	Reproducibility %	Expanded uncertainty (k=2)
METAS	1.082	0.41	0.025
VSL	0.992	0.47	0.026
VTT	0.952	0.72	0.026

Figure 6: Representation of the average slope values of the PTB spectroscopic measurements and associated uncertainty determined for the three NH₃ generators from METAS, VSL and VTT in wet air.

2.5.3 Comparison of the results obtained in wet and dry air

VSL and METAS generators were used in the two comparisons on dry and wet air. The average slopes obtained for wet and dry NH₃ reference gas mixtures with VSL and METAS generators versus the PTB spectroscopic measurements are compared on the figure 6.

Figure 6: Comparison of the average slopes between dry and wet gas for VSL and METAS RGMs

The figure 6 shows that biases of -2.3% for METAS and -1.5% for VSL are observed for the average slopes between generated NH_3 amount fractions and PTB spectroscopic measurement results considering dry and wet air.

2.6 Conclusion

The aim of this study was to compare reference generators based on different principles (dynamic dilution of gravimetric gas mixtures, permeation and liquid evaporation) using spectroscopic measurements between 0 and $400 \text{ nmol}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ in dry and wet air for NH_3 which is a very challenging pollutant because of its reactivity and its adsorption/desorption phenomenon.

The obtained results showed that, overall, the generators are operating correctly with a good reproducibility (better than 0.8% in dry and wet air) and a good linearity on the measurement range from 0 to $400 \text{ nmol}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ in dry and wet air. The expanded uncertainties (0.023 to 0.031) on the slope of the regression line between the amount fractions of the generated gas mixtures and PTB spectroscopic measurement results are consistent for all gas generators.

Considering dry and wet air biases of around -3% for METAS and VSL are observed for the average slopes between generated NH_3 amount fractions and the results of the spectroscopic measurements. Furthermore, this comparison shows that the amount fractions stability takes more time to achieve for the reference generators based on the dynamic dilution of gravimetric gas mixtures.

3 Performance of commercial analysers for NH_3 , CH_4 and CO_2 : linearity and repeatability (A131; A. Pogany, PTB)

Linearity and repeatability of commercial cavity ring down spectrometers have been tested for measurements in the laboratory for:

- (1) NH_3 : PTB performed linearity and repeatability tests up to a few $\mu\text{mol}/\text{mol}$ using a Picarro G2103 analyser with PTB's improved spectral evaluation algorithm as reference, while VTT tested linearity and repeatability from a few nmol/mol up to a few $\mu\text{mol}/\text{mol}$ of a Tiger Optics and a Picarro G2103 analyser using wet reference gas from the VTT reference gas generator from A1.1.2
- (2) CH_4 and CO_2 : EMPA performed linearity and repeatability tests up to a few $\mu\text{mol}/\text{mol}$ on a Picarro G2401 analyser using calibration gas standards.

3.1 NH_3

PTB has performed linearity and repeatability tests up to $200 \text{ nmol}/\text{mol}$ in 2014 and 2015 within the Met NH_3 project. Further measurements in the 0-400 nmol/mol range were performed in summer 2024 in Task 1.2. of the quantiAGREMI project. Results of these two measurements agree very well and show very good linearity of the analyser.

To test the applicability of the spectrometer for measuring higher NH_3 amount fractions, tests has been carried out up to $25 \mu\text{mol}/\text{mol}$ at PTB in 2024. These tests showed that the measurement range can be extended at least up to $25 \mu\text{mol}/\text{mol}$ without any modifications in the hardware. The data evaluation scheme has been updated to accommodate the whole amount fraction range from 0 to $25 \mu\text{mol}/\text{mol}$. The instrument shows very good linearity and accuracy in the higher amount fraction range as well. Furthermore, the slopes of the linear regression agree well in the two concentration ranges.

Figure 7: NH₃ amount fractions measured by the Picarro G2103 spectrometer as a function of NH₃ amount fraction provided by PTB’s spectral evaluation method (optical gas standard, OGS)

An offset of ~0.62 nmol/mol has been observed, and most of it turned out to be an artefact of the data evaluation method of the spectrometer. The offset could be decreased to ~0.12 nmol/mol with PTB’s spectral fitting algorithm.

Figure 8: NH₃ amount fractions measured in zero gas (purified ambient air) by a commercial Picarro G2103 spectrometer and with PTB’s spectral evaluation

VTT used the reference gas generator based on evaporation method from A1.1.2 to test commercial optical CRDS analysers by Tiger Optics and Picarro for ammonia. In order to generate a humid calibration gas, ammonia solutions with known concentration are evaporated into a stream of pressurized carrier gas. Solution flow rate is controlled using a stepper motor-controlled syringe pump and a mass flow controller is used for the carrier gas dosing. The solution and the carrier gas are mixed in a nozzle, which then sprays the mixture to an evaporator in elevated temperature made from carefully selected materials to minimize adsorption to surfaces. Typical output flow rate for the reference gas is 7 litres/minute (range 4 – 10 litres/minute) with water of content 0.1 – 1.5 vol-%. In these experiments purified instrument air is used as a carrier gas i.e., matrix gas. Tested ammonia concentration range extends several orders of magnitude, from 0.4 ppb to 10 ppm. Figure 9 shows all measurement points for both instruments.

Figure 9: NH₃ amount fractions measured by a commercial Picarro and a Tiger Optics spectrometer as a function of the reference NH₃ amount fractions provided by VTT’s evaporation generator

These results reveal wide operation range and high degree of linearity for both tested CRDS analysers. Some offset was observed, which can also be a result from memory effect for a sticky molecule like ammonia inside the analysers, sampling system or the reference gas generator.

3.2 CO₂ and CH₄:

At Empa linearity and repeatability of a G2401 CRDS analyser were repeatedly tested over several years using calibration gases shown in Table 3.

The calibration standards for greenhouse gases were produced at Empa by blending defined volumes of two commercial standards (SG1: 3005 ppm CH₄, 1000 ppm CO, 90.2 ppm N₂O in CO₂; SG2: 9% CH₄, 231 ppm CO, 75.4 ppm N₂O in CO₂, Messer Schweiz AG) with a defined mass of commercial pressurized air into 50 L Luxfer aluminium cylinders (P2862Z, Matar, Italy). Concentrations of CO₂, CH₄, N₂O and CO were analysed by the World Calibration Centre for Surface Ozone, Carbon Monoxide, Methane and Carbon Dioxide (WCC Empa) by QCLAS and CRDS against NOAA/GMD standards on accepted calibration scales (Novelli *et al.*, 1991; Dlugokencky *et al.*, 2005; Hall *et al.*, 2007).

Table 3: Greenhouse gas concentrations in calibration standards as analysed by WCC-Empa. The indicated precision is the standard deviation for repeated measurements (n = 3).

Cylinder	CO ₂ [ppm]	CH ₄ [ppb]	N ₂ O [ppb]	CO [ppb]
D337300	430.4 ± 0.06	2070.7 ± 0.3	326.8 ± 0.03	209.4 ± 0.3
D337302	578.0 ± 0.03	6805.9 ± 10.4	339.2 ± 0.06	327.7 ± 0.3
D337303	727.2 ± 0.04	11537.0 ± 21.7	351.0 ± 0.11	443.2 ± 0.2
D337301	1017.6 ± 0.04	20947.8 ± 43.9	375.9 ± 0.26	668.5 ± 0.2

As it is summarized in Table 4, the analyser demonstrated excellent linearity within 0.995 – 1.002 for CH₄ and 0.991 – 0.997 for CO₂ and minimal offset, < 0.009 ppm for CH₄ and < 2.2 ppm for CO₂. Repeatability tests conducted in an air-conditioned trailer at EVS, Agroscope Tänikon, indicate that drift effects of the uncalibrated data for three measurement campaigns per year were well within the analyser specifications for CO₂ and mostly within specifications for CH₄. Figure 10 and 11 shows long-term drift effects over more than three years, which were ≤ 0.5 ppm for CO₂ and ≤ 10 ppb for CH₄.

Table 4: Calibration factors for CH₄ and CO₂ analysis by CRDS (G2401, Picarro Inc.)

Calibration factors		2015	2020	2023
CH ₄	Slope	0.9947 ± 0.0003	0.99669 ± 0.00142	1.0022 ± 0.00016
	Intercept	0.009 ± 0.004 ppm	-0.004806 ± 0.0186 ppm	0.0025 ± 0.00210 ppm
CO ₂	Slope	0.9943 ± 0.0006	0.99145 ± 0.00344	0.9968 ± 0.00016
	Intercept	1.0 ± 0.4 ppm	-2.1373 ± 2.19 ppm	0.0571 ± 0.10671 ppm

Figure 10: CO₂ measurement by CRDS without prior calibration (top) and with calibration (bottom) compared to instrument specifications (red line).

Figure 11: CH₄ measurement by CRDS without prior calibration (top) and with calibration (bottom) compared to instrument specifications (red line).

3.3 Conclusions

The tested commercial CRDS instruments show good linearity, small drift, often even better than manufacturer specifications. Offsets might be significant for NH_3 measurements in the lower ppb range. Users should consider the importance of the matrix gas composition to achieve accurate results.

4 A132: Interference tests for NH_3 , CH_4 and CO_2 (A132; J. Fritsche, METAS)

4.1 Objective

Using the gas bench of INRAE (optimized according to A1.1.3) METAS and INRAE have tested if interferences between NH_3 or CH_4 or CO_2 are occurring when measuring with Picarro CRDS analysers.

Interferences were evaluated by adding controlled amounts of CH_4 , NH_3 , CO_2 , N_2O and condensed 'air' from livestock housing to the gas mixtures using the improved bench. CH_4 , CO_2 and N_2O were added from cylinders, NH_3 was generated using METAS' reference gas analyser ReGaS (upgraded according to A1.1.2).

4.2 Experimental setup

Figure 12: Gas bench of INRAE used for investigating interferences of CO_2 , CH_4 , N_2O and H_2O on NH_3 .

In this campaign the effect of CO_2 , CH_4 , N_2O and H_2O on NH_3 amount fractions measured with a Picarro G2103 analyser was investigated. Due to limited time, the effects of NH_3 , CH_4 and N_2O on measured CO_2 amount fractions as well as the effects of NH_3 , CO_2 and N_2O on measured CH_4 amount fractions could not be explored. Additionally, condensed 'air' was not available during the experimental campaign. However, air from a test compartment of INRAE's experimental housing loaded with digested slurry was sampled as part of A1.3.5.

For the interference tests gas mixtures with the amount fractions listed in Table 5 were generated dynamically. The total flow rate of the gas mixture was set to 8000 ml/min STP and the setpoints of the MFC's of INRAE's gas bench were determined accordingly. The MFCs of the gases not used for a mixture were closed.

While NH_3 , CO_2 , CH_4 and N_2O were provided by bottled, single component gas mixtures in N_2 matrix, water vapor was generated continuously by passing dry N_2 through a Nafion humidifier flushed with deionized, temperature-controlled water. Other than suggested in A1.3.2, NH_3 was supplied by a bottled mixture in N_2 matrix and not by METAS' dynamic reference gas generator.

Table 5: Amount of substance fractions combined for the interference tests.

Combination	NH ₃ μmol/mol	H ₂ O mg/l	CO ₂ μmol/mol	CH ₄ μmol/mol	N ₂ O μmol/mol
N ₂ + NH ₃ 2nd	6				
N ₂ + NH ₃ 3rd	6				
N ₂ + NH ₃ + H ₂ O	6	9			
N ₂ + NH ₃ + CO ₂	6		500		
N ₂ + NH ₃ + CO ₂ (750 ppm)	6		750		
N ₂ + NH ₃ + CH ₄	6			10	
N ₂ + NH ₃ + N ₂ O	6				1

Table 6 and Figure 13 show the measured NH₃ amount of substance fractions without and with the addition of H₂O, CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O. The measurement uncertainties are reported as expanded measurement uncertainties U (k=2). The uncertainties include the calibration uncertainties of the MFCs used to generate the gas mixtures and the precision of the Picarro analysers. As only relative amount fractions are investigated, the uncertainties of the parent gas mixtures are ignored.

Table 6: Mean, standard deviation and number of measurement points (n) of the measured NH₃ amount of substance fractions for the investigated gas mixtures.

Combination	Mean nmol/mol	SD nmol/mol	SD Relative	n
N ₂ + NH ₃ 2nd	5499.67	19.11	0.35%	599
N ₂ + NH ₃ 3rd	5493.24	16.54	0.30%	602
N ₂ + NH ₃ + H ₂ O	5629.59	10.38	0.18%	578
N ₂ + NH ₃ + CO ₂	5561.95	9.86	0.18%	655
N ₂ + NH ₃ + CO ₂ (750 ppm)	5557.97	7.50	0.13%	653
N ₂ + NH ₃ + CH ₄	5537.70	10.84	0.20%	634
N ₂ + NH ₃ + N ₂ O	5531.77	8.16	0.15%	611

Figure 13: Mean \pm U (k=2) of NH₃ amount of substance fractions in the investigated gas mixtures relative to NH₃ in N₂.

4.3 Observations

In the present experiment, H₂O appeared to have a significant effect on NH₃ amount fractions. However, as the humid gas flow was measured upstream of the humidifier and merged with the other gases downstream of the humidifier, errors due to the added water vapor volume may have been introduced. Thus, the effect of H₂O reported here should be verified with a different humidification method, e.g., liquid water addition and evaporation.

Uncertainties of MFC calibrations are dominant, which is reflected by the similar uncertainties displayed in Figure 13. The uncertainty of the Picarro analyser only adds marginally to the total uncertainty.

Addition of H₂O, CO₂, CH₄ or N₂O appear to reduce signal noise considerably (see standard deviations in Table 6). The cause of this effect is not clear but could be linked to the use of N₂ as matrix gas. The Picarro CRDS is designed for NH₃ analysis in air – using it with N₂ may change signal noise. It is known that the Picarro CRDS returns NH₃ amount fractions approx. 10% lower in N₂ than in air, due to different width of spectral lines (discussion with Andrea Pogany, PTB, November 2024).

5 Improvement of NH₃, CH₄, and CO₂ measurements in livestock housings: filters and tubing (A133; J. Fritsche, METAS)

5.1 Objective

Within the scope of A1.3.3 the suitability of different filters and tubing materials for sampling of air containing NH₃, CH₄ and CO₂ in livestock housings was determined.

5.2 Material selection

The selection of tubing and filter materials and to be tested was based on the JRP EMRP ENV55 MetNH₃ project, experience of project participants, information gained from scientific publications and feedback from stakeholders. Besides their compatibility with NH₃, CH₄ and CO₂, other aspects like cost, mechanical stability and environmental impact for production and disposal were considered.

5.3 Experimental setup

The suitability tests were performed at the experimental housing of Agroscope in Tänikon, Switzerland in Summer 2024.

5.3.1 NH₃ analysers

A State-of-the-art Picarro G2103 CRDS of METAS with SilcoNert® 2000 coated sample gas lines and integrated humidity correction (Serial-Nr. 1283-AEDS2035; upgraded 2019; purchased 2012) was used together with a standard Picarro G2103 CRDS of Agroscope (Serial-Nr. 3947-AHDS2179; purchased 2021).

The state-of-the-art Picarro of METAS was calibrated with a magnetic suspension balance and a NH₃ permeation tube (ID: NH3_W566_022) in the range of 50 to 700 nmol/mol. The standard Picarro of Agroscope was calibrated by loading NH₃-sensitive denuders mounted in a sampling air stream and analysis of the washing solution by ion-exchange chromatography. The calibration range is from 0 to 4000 nmol/mol.

The following tubing types were selected for the tests:

- PFA ¼" (OD), 30 m, provided by METAS
- Stainless steel ¼" (OD), SilcoNert® 2000 coated, 30 m, provided by METAS
- Dekabon ¼" (OD, PE-aluminium compound with PE inner coating), 30 m, provided by METAS
- The following filters were selected for the tests:

At the sampling inlet a PTFE filter of type TE 38 MF 37 MM (VWR 516-5022), pore size 5 µm, in cellulose ester filter housing was used. For some tests a sintered stainless steel SilcoNert® 2000 coated 0.5-µm Swagelok filter was mounted at inlet of the state-of-the-art Picarro of METAS. Both Picarro instruments are internally equipped with PTFE 0.015 µm (Wafergard® GT-Plus) filters.

5.3.2 Sampling

For comparing tubing and filter materials the sampling lines (PFA, stainless steel and Dekabon) were guided from the air-conditioned instrument trailer into one compartment of the experimental housing. An inlet filter was attached to each tube. A switch box with PTFE solenoid valved was mounted upstream of the Picarro analysers to swap sampling lines. The sampling lines were flushed at a flow rate of 8 l/min with the Picarro's drawing a sub-flow.

To determine the offset between the analysers and the tubing materials, the switch box was configured in such a way that both analysers sampled the same tube. The sampled tube was switched every 60 minutes (see Figure 14).

Figure 14: Setup used to compare tubing of different materials

5.4 Results

5.4.1 Effects of particle filters

During the entire test period 5- μ m PTFE particle filters in cellulose ester filter housings were mounted to the tubing inlets. Additionally, a SolcoNert[®] coated, 0.5- μ m sintered metal filter was mounted to the state-of-the-art Picarro inlet for additional instrument protection.

The additional sintered metal filter introduced a lag in the analyser response, especially at NH_3 levels below approx. 500 nmol/mol (see Figures 15 and 16). Performing a cross-correlation analysis, this lag had a magnitude of about 10 seconds, i.e., the state-of-the-art Picarro of METAS was approx. 10 seconds behind.

Figure 15: Time lag of measured NH_3 amount fractions when no sintered metal filter is mounted at the METAS state of the art analyser.

Figure 16: Time lag of measured NH₃ amount fractions when a sintered metal filter is mounted at the METAS state of the art analyser.

5.4.2 Differences between tubing materials

As an alternative to PFA, SolcoNert® coated stainless steel and Dekabon (inner coating PE) tubing were tested. In two separate experiments air was sampled via 30-m long tubing, each with PFA as the reference.

Coated stainless steel did not increase the time lag, i.e., air sampled by stainless steel tubing reached the analyser approx. 10 seconds later than sampled by PFA tubing (see Figure 17). On the other hand, the Dekabon tubing produced a much larger time lag of about one minute (see Figure 18).

This time lag results in a spread of the recorded NH₃ amount fractions, which increases considerably with decreasing amount fractions. This effect is even more pronounced when using Dekabon tubing.

Figure 17: Time lag of measured NH₃ amount fractions in air sampled by PFA and coated stainless steel tubing.

Figure 18: Time lag of measured NH_3 amount fractions in air sampled by PFA and Dekabon tubing.

5.5 Conclusions

Different tubing materials were tested to assess their suitability for use in livestock housings. SilcoNert® coated stainless steel and lower-priced, halogen-free Dekabon tubing were compared to established PFA tubing.

It could be shown that SilcoNert® coated stainless steel and PFA tubing produced similar results, whereas Dekabon tubing introduced a considerable time lag of up to approx. 1 minute; only high ammonia peaks yielded matching amount fractions with a negligible time lag. Thus, for applications where the smallest changes in NH_3 amount fractions need to be detected, PFA and SilcoNert® coated stainless steel remain the tubing material of choice.

Due to availability and cost, experiments were performed with 30-m long $\frac{1}{4}$ " tubing. Using larger tubes would decrease the surface to volume ratio, reducing the negative effects of Dekabon. With its mechanical stability and low cost, Dekabon would be a favourable material for in-situ applications once it would be available with a superior inner coating.

6 Improvement of CH_4 reference measurements in livestock housings: detecting small differences and effect of ambient conditions (A134; R. Högström, VTT, A. Bayat, LUKE)

6.1 Objective

A comprehensive field-study on the performance of a wide range of measuring instruments for measuring livestock emissions was carried out at LUKE research barn in Jokioinen Finland during 7.2. - 13.2.2024. The aim was to investigate the suitability of different measuring technologies for this specific application, as well as to develop a fit for purpose method for reliable sampling in field conditions. The emissions and compounds of interest were methane (CH_4), ammonia (NH_3), nitrous oxide (N_2O), carbon dioxide (CO_2) and water (H_2O).

6.2 Tested measurement technologies

A list of tested measuring instruments is given in Table 1.

Table 7: Measuring instruments evaluated for suitability for livestock emissions measurements.

Measurement instrument	Measured parameters	Description
Photoacoustic Spectroscopy	CH ₄ , NH ₃ , N ₂ O, CO ₂ , H ₂ O	Photoacoustic
Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy	CH ₄ , NH ₃ , N ₂ O, CO ₂ , H ₂ O	FTIR
Cavity Ring-Down Spectroscopy	CH ₄ , H ₂ O	CRDS
Capacitive thin-film polymer sensors	H ₂ O	HMP9
Non-Dispersive Infrared spectroscopy sensor	CO ₂	GMP252
Non-Dispersive Infrared spectroscopy	N ₂ O, CO ₂ , H ₂ O	1229, 158C
Non-Dispersive Infrared spectroscopy	CH ₄ , CO ₂ , H ₂ O	138E, 146D

The instruments were not calibrated before the measurements. In this study, the time-dependent response of the instruments was considered the most important parameter when assessing the instruments' ability to track emissions in livestock housing. In the actual measurement campaigns later in the project, instruments were calibrated to reduce systematic errors.

6.3 Measurement setup

The analysers were sharing the same sampling line and the sensors (HMP9 and GMP252) were located close to the sampling point inside the barn to ensure a uniform air sampling (Figure 19).

As calibration gases reference gas cylinders for methane (CH₄, 800 ppm ± 1%, AGA, Finland) and carbon dioxide (CO₂, 5000 ppm ± 1%, AGA, Finland) were used. Ammonia and water vapour calibration gases were generated using VTT trace gas generator, which is based on the evaporation and flow mixing technique. The tested gas analysers were connected in parallel drawing their sample gas from the same sampling line, while the sensors were located next to the sampling line inlet. The tested gas analysers had their own internal pump sucking sample air from the sampling line. Teflon tubing was used for the sampling lines. During calibration measurements, the calibration gas was connected to the sampling line with a slight overflow to the exhaust.

Figure 19. Setup of analysers, sampling lines and sensors used for testing the technologies.

6.4 Results

Results of the online measurements are summarized in Figures 20 – 28.

6.4.1 Results for methane (CH₄)

From the measurement results presented in Figure 20 it can be seen that all instruments are able to detect methane concentrations in the order of 100 – 300 ppm. Moreover, all instruments are able to track the temporal changes in methane concentrations. However, there is a significant offset in the concentration levels measured with the different sensor technologies, underlining the importance of SI traceable calibrations.

Figure 20: Measurement results for methane. Concentrations given in ppm.

To investigate this offset in detail, a calibration gas with known SI traceable methane concentration was provided to the inlet of the measuring instruments. Results of the calibration measurements (Figure 21), clearly show that the high-end, and more expensive, devices based on CRDS, PAS and FTIR provide more accurate readings, i.e., readings closer to the true concentration given by the calibration gas. The best match was found for the CRDS device, which was chosen as the reference instrument for upcoming measurement campaigns in the project. Low-cost sensors based on NDIR technology show 35 % up to 85 % lower values compared to the reference concentration of the calibration gas. However, with proper calibration, these devices provide a viable and cost-effective solution for livestock emission measurements.

Figure 21: Measurement results with reference gas (test gas) input. Concentrations given in ppm.

6.4.2 Results for ammonia (NH₃)

Measurement results for ammonia (NH₃) show a different temporal response for the Photoacoustic and FTIR instrument (Figure 22). From the results it is, however, not possible to say whether the temporal change measured by the photoacoustic is reflecting the true variation in the concentration.

Figure 22: Measurement results for ammonia. Concentrations given in ppm.

A calibration measurement was performed using the VTT trace gas generator as a traceable reference for ammonia. The FTIR response was equivalent to the generated test gas concentration of around 6.4 ppm (Figure 22). The photoacoustic instrument showed 25 % lower values. Interestingly, the photoacoustic method measured higher concentrations compared to the FTIR device during the actual measurements (Figure 22) and lower values during the calibration measurements. Repeated measurements (not shown here) indicate that the FTIR measurements are more consistent than the photoacoustic measurements when compared to the reference value generated by the VTT trace gas generator. The reactive nature of NH₃ and its tendency to adsorb to surfaces might also explain differences in the response of the devices.

Figure 23: Measurement results with VTT trace gas generator input. Concentrations given in ppm.

6.4.3 Results for nitrous oxide (N₂O)

Measurement results for Nitrous oxide (N₂O) show a very different response for the tested technologies (Figure 24). The photoacoustic and FTIR devices measured very low concentrations around 0.4 – 1.2 ppm. On the other hand, NDIR devices show much higher concentrations in the order of 3 – 7 ppm and a larger temporal variation in concentrations compared to Photoacoustic and FTIR. The accuracy of the results could not be

verified due to the absence of a calibration gas. Anyhow, the measured concentrations are close to the detections limit of the NDIR devices, which might explain the large variations observed in the results.

Figure 24: Measurement results for nitrous oxide. Concentrations given in ppm.

6.4.4 Results for carbon dioxide (CO₂)

Measurement results for Carbon dioxide (CO₂) show that all devices are able to track the temporal changes in CO₂ concentrations in the range from 1800 ppm to 2800 ppm. (Figure 25). However, there is a significant offset in the sensor readings. All tested sensors show lower concentration values compared to the reference value provided by a certified gas mixture (Figure 26). Surprisingly, the low-cost NDIR devices, in most cases, show a better agreement with the reference value compared to more expensive FTIR and Photoacoustic devices.

Figure 25: Measurement results for carbon dioxide. Concentrations given in ppm.

Figure 26: Measurement results with reference gas (test gas) input. Concentrations given in ppm.

6.4.5 Results for water (H₂O)

Also with water, large variations in measured concentrations were observed for different measurement instruments (Figure 27). All devices were able to track temporal changes in the water concentration. Based on the calibration measurements using the VTT trace gas generator as a traceable reference for the water concentration (Figure 28), the high-end measurement technologies, i.e., CRDS, FTIR and Photoacoustic, show a better agreement with the reference value compared to the low-cost NDIR based devices, which can deviate more than 50 % from the reference value.

Figure 27: Measurement results for water. Concentrations are given as volume fraction in %.

Figure 28: Measurement results with VTT trace gas generator input. Concentrations are given as volume fraction in %.

6.5 Conclusions

A comprehensive study on the performance of a wide range of measuring instruments, including CRDS, Photoacoustic, FTIR, NDIR and capacitive thin-film polymer sensors, show that the applied sampling methodology is well suited for measuring emissions from livestock production. All devices were able track temporal variations in the concentrations, except for Ammonia (NH_3) and Nitrous oxide (N_2O), which were present at very low concentrations. Calibration measurements using SI traceable reference gases show that high-end devices, i.e., CRDS, Photoacoustic and FTIR, provide in general a better agreement with the reference value compared to low-cost sensors based on NDIR technology. However, an offset in the readings of low-cost sensors can be compensated based on a traceable calibration, which makes these low-cost devices a viable solution for continuous monitoring of livestock emissions.

7 Comparison of state-of-the-art reference NH_3 measurement device with currently used measurement device in the livestock housings (A135; J. Fritsche, METAS)

7.1 Background

Ammonia measurements in the air of livestock housings are challenging for both, sampling and analytics. Besides NH_3 adsorption on filters, tubing and particles floating in the sampled air stream, water vapor may cause interferences in the analysed NH_3 spectra. Other than that, the sampling points have to be representative while being protected from animal access.

Additionally, in common naturally ventilated housing systems with large openings, the amount fractions are near to ambient and thus the gradient to the outside air is very small. Consequently, the calibration of the measurement instruments needs to be very accurate at low amount fractions and cover a large measurement range.

7.2 Objective

The aim of this activity was to compare a state-of-the-art Picarro CRDS NH_3 analyser with standard Picarro and Proceas CRDS instruments. By comparing the temporal trends of NH_3 amount fractions of the different instruments in livestock housings, potential shortcomings like responsivity, sensitivity, etc. may be identified.

The comparison measurements were done in the naturally ventilated experimental housing of WBF-Agroscope, Switzerland, and the experimental facility of INRAE in Rennes. In both facilities, the instruments sampled air from the same volume within the livestock housings.

7.3 Comparison of state-of-the-art Picarro CRDS with standard Picarro CRDS

7.3.1 Experimental setup

For the experiments in the naturally ventilated housing of WBF-Agroscope, a state-of-the-art Picarro G2103 CRDS of METAS (sample gas lines SilcoNert® 2000 coated; integrated humidity correction, Serial-Nr. 1283-AEDS2035; upgraded 2019; purchased 2012) was compared to a standard Picarro G2103 CRDS of WBF-Agroscope (Serial-Nr. 3947-AHDS2179; purchased 2021).

The state-of-the-art Picarro of METAS was calibrated with a magnetic suspension balance and a NH₃ permeation tube (ID: NH₃_W566_022) in the range of 50 to 700 nmol/mol. The standard Picarro of Agroscope was calibrated by loading NH₃-sensitive denuders mounted in a sampling air stream and analysis of the washing solution by ion-exchange chromatography. The calibration range was from 0 to 4000 nmol/mol.

For comparing the Picarro NH₃ analysers, the existing sampling network of the experimental housing of WBF-Agroscope was used (see Figure 29). The state-of-the-art Picarro G2103 of METAS was installed parallel to the instruments of WBF-Agroscope to sample air from compartment 1 (left section). During the experiments in September 2024 an average relative humidity of 70% was recorded.

Figure 29: Location of the state-of-the-art Picarro of METAS and the standard Picarro of WBF-Agroscope in the experimental housing. The instruments measured in parallel when air was sampled from the left section, where 24 inlets are merged to the main sampling line.

7.4 Results

As shown in Figure 30, the two instruments compared well with a slope of 0.997 after calibration correction. The correction reduced the offset from 6.48 to -13.1 nmol/mol.

Figure 30: Comparison of 1-minute-mean NH_3 amount fractions of the state-of-the-art METAS Picarro and the WBF-Agroscope standard Picarro before (top) and after (bottom) calibration correction.

7.5 Comparison Picarro CRDS with Proceas CRDS

7.5.1 Experimental setup

For the comparison of the state-of-the-art Picarro CRDS of METAS with the standard Proceas CRDS of INRAE, air was sampled from an experimental compartment of the livestock housing at INRAE's Saint-Gilles site. As substrate, digested slurry was spread in the compartment. Air sampling was switched between the in- and outlet of the compartment every 2 hours.

7.5.2 Results

Due to technical problems of the PROCEAS CRDS analyser, only a short period of simultaneous measurements was valid for comparison. Figure 31 shows the NH_3 amount fractions recorded during this period. The oscillating signal reflects the heating cycle of the experimental compartment. It can be seen that this cycle is captured well by the state-of-the-art Picarro, while the standard Proceas seems not to be able to resolve this oscillation. Other than that, the response of the standard Proceas to shifts of NH_3 amount fractions between <1 and $30 \mu\text{mol/mol}$, i.e., between in- and outlet air, is very slow compared to the Picarro instrument.

Figure 31: NH_3 amount fractions in air sampled from digested slurry with a state-of-the-art Picarro CRDS and a standard Proceas CRDS.

7.5.3 Conclusions

To assess the performance of a state-of-the-art to a standard Picarro CRDS analyser, ammonia amount fractions were measured in an experimental livestock housing in summer 2024. The state-of-the-art Picarro of METAS and the standard instrument of Agroscope continuously sampled indoor air with a relative humidity around 70% and NH_3 amount fractions up to approx. $12 \mu\text{mol/mol}$.

No shortcoming of the standard Picarro relative to the state-of-the-art Picarro could be observed. Overall, the two instruments matched well during the comparison period, although the analysers were calibrated with different methods (permeator + balance vs. denuder + ion exchange chromatography). The observed offset of -13.1 nmol/mol would require closer analysis but might be explained by the different calibration methods.

The equivalence of a standard Proceas CRDS and a state-of-the-art Picarro CRDS was tested by sampling air emitted from digested slurry spread in an experimental compartment.

The experiments showed that the standard Proceas CRDS could not resolve fluctuations of the NH_3 amount fraction with periods of up to several minutes. Also, after amount fraction shifts in the lower $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ range the Proceas required several hours to stabilize.

These results suggests that the standard Proceas CRDS does not match the performance of a standard Picarro CRDS in terms of signal response. However, a fast response at high NH_3 amount fractions as observed in livestock housings is essential to quantify cumulative emissions.

8 Validation of new halogenated tracer gas (A136; J. Mohn, Empa)

8.1 Tracer gases currently used for emission quantification

Currently SF_6 (and SF_5CF_3) are two widely used external tracer gases applied for emission estimates using the tracer ratio technique. Within quantiAGREMI, less harmful alternatives were evaluated by Empa,

considering environmental impact (e.g., GWP), toxicity, analytics (e.g., sensitivity) and legal restrictions of candidate substances. In addition, the candidate substances must be normally absent or at low concentrations in livestock housings. Table 8 shows important identifiers of currently used tracer gases.

Table 8: Identifiers and important properties for currently used tracer gases, SF₆ and SF₅CF₃.

Formula	Substance	CAS	Molecular mass [g mol ⁻¹]	GWP (100 years)	Ambient abundance
SF ₆	Sulfur hexafluoride	2551-62-4	146.05	26'087	8 ppt
SF ₅ CF ₃	Trifluoromethylsulfur pentafluoride	373-80-8	196.06	17'700	0.15 ppt

Tracer concentrations ([Tracer]_{dosed}) and flows (flow_{tracer}) dosed in the Agroscope experimental dairy housing (EDH) have been adjusted in a way, that tracer concentrations analysed by GC-ECD for both strong and weak ventilation fall in the optimal range of the analytics (Table 9) (Mohn *et al.*, 2018).

Table 9: Analytics, detection limit, target concentration range (minimum, maximum) and concentration as well as flows of the SF₆ and SF₅CF₃ tracer gases applied in the Agroscope EDH.

Formula	Analytics	Detection limit	Tracer concentration analytics [Tracer] _{GC}		Tracer dosing		
			minimal	maximum	[Tracer] _{dosed}	flow _{tracer}	
SF ₆	GC-ECD	2 ppt	50 ppt	1'500 ppt	2'000 ppm	200 mL min ⁻¹	2016 L / week (0.27 cylinders @ 50 L, 150 bar)
SF ₅ CF ₃	GC-ECD	2 ppt	50 ppt	1'500 ppt	2'000 ppm	200 mL min ⁻¹	2016 L / week (0.27 cylinders @ 50 L, 150 bar)

The dilution ratio (D) for the tracer was calculated for conditions of weak / strong ventilation from the dosed tracer concentration ([Tracer]_{dosed}) and the tracer concentration analysed by GC-ECD ([Tracer]_{GC}, maximum range, minimum range) following Eq. 1. Ventilation rate and dilution ratio mainly depend on wind speed and size of openings. Alternatively, D can be expressed by the quotient of the air flow through the housing (flow_{housing}), divided by the flow of the tracer (flow_{tracer}).

$$D = [\text{Tracer}]_{\text{dosed}} / [\text{Tracer}]_{\text{GC}} = \text{flow}_{\text{housing}} / \text{flow}_{\text{tracer}}$$

The dilution ratios D for the tracer gases for strong and weak ventilation are 40'000'000 and 2'000'000. From this the air flows through the housing (flow_{housing}) can be calculated for strong and weak ventilation as 8'000 m³ min⁻¹ and 400 m³ min⁻¹. These characteristics have to be considered evaluating alternative tracer gases for the Agroscope EDH.

8.2 Selection of less harmful alternative tracer gases

Alternative tracer gases must have a low environmental footprint (low GWP, non-toxic), low and stable ambient abundance, no source in dairy houses and be commercially available in sufficient quantities and at reasonable price. In addition, commercial and affordable analytics have to be at hand, with continuous analysis being a plus. From the evaluated gases shown in table 10 ethane (C₂H₆) and ethine (C₂H₂) are most suitable to replace established tracer gases. The full list of evaluated tracer gases is much more extended and provided in the project report A1.1.8.

Table 10: Identifiers and important properties for selected alternative tracer gases. Critical parameters are indicated in orange, selected tracer gases are highlighted in green.

Formula	CAS	GWP (100 yrs)	Ambient abundance	Analytics	Consumption / Costs for typical application in EVS	Comments
CF ₄	75-73-0	7349	-	-		GWP too high
CH ₂ F ₂	75-10-5	677	32 ppt	GC-ECD / FID	10% CH ₂ F ₂ 4 L min ⁻¹	GWP high, high detection limit and low temporal resolution expected
C ₃ H ₂ F ₄	754-12-1	< 1	0.1 ppt	Gasera	10% C ₃ H ₂ F ₄ 4 L min ⁻¹ / approx. 4'500 CHF per 2-3 weeks for pure C ₃ H ₂ F ₄	Price for tracer gas too high
Xe	7440-63-3	0	87 ppb	QMS	Pure Xe 6.4 L min ⁻¹ / approx. 60 CHF L ⁻¹	Price for tracer gas much too high
COS	463-58-1	-	500 ppt	Aeris MIRA ULTRA	1% COS 0.4 L min ⁻¹	Toxicity too high
¹⁵ N ¹⁴ NO	10024-97-2	298	1.2 ppb	CRDS	1% ¹⁵ N ¹⁴ NO 0.1 L min ⁻¹ / approx. 40'000 CHF per week for pure ¹⁵ N ¹⁴ NO	Price for tracer gas much too high
C ₂ H ₆	74-84-0	-	1.5 ppb (stable background)	Aeris MIRA Ultra, CRDS	100% 0.4 L min ⁻¹ ; 0.3 cylinders @ 50 L per week	Selected option
C ₂ H ₂	74-86-2	-	2 ppb (many events in bkg)	Aeris MIRA Ultra, CRDS	Similar to C ₂ H ₆	Alternative option but higher variations in background concentrations

8.3 Analytics and validation of tracer gas analysis

Empa acquired a MIRA Ultra mid-infrared laser absorption spectrometer (Aeris Technologies, S/N 100641) for CH₄ / C₂H₆ analysis with a specified sensitivity of < 1 ppb/s CH₄ and < 500 ppt/s C₂H₆. The analyser operates in a concentration range of 10 ppb to 10'000 ppm CH₄ and 1 to 1000 ppt C₂H₆ at a temporal resolution of 1 – 2 Hz (standard) or 10 Hz (optional). The actual precision of the analyser was determined in an Allan precision experiment (Figure 32). The results also indicate the need for regular drift correction, e.g., every 30-60 minutes to limit detrimental drift effects.

Figure 32: Optimal averaging time and Allan precision of the MIRA ULTRA analyser: (a) 100 s averaging provides 25 ppt and 110 ppt precision for C_2H_6 (left) and CH_4 (right). The WMO/GAW network compatibility goal is 2 ppb for CH_4 .

In November 2023 we initiated CH_4 / C_2H_6 measurements in ambient air from a rooftop air inlet (approx. 15 meters above ground) at the Empa research campus in Dübendorf, Switzerland. To minimize water vapor interferences, sample and calibration gases were passed through a Nafion dryer (Perma Pure MD-070-48S-4). To correct for drift effects and calibrate the analyser, two cylinders of compressed air were analysed; reference gas 1 with 2.09 ppm CH_4 and 1.54 ppb C_2H_6 , and reference gas 2 with 2.39 ppm CH_4 and 10.8 ppb C_2H_6 . Reference gas 1 was analysed once per hour, reference gas 2 twice daily. Analysis of reference gases was for 10 minutes per application.

Temporal trends of CH_4 concentrations obtained from the MIRA Ultra and a Picarro CRDS device (model 2401) are in excellent agreement (Figure 33, top). Time series of C_2H_6 concentrations from the MIRA Ultra analyser and a GC-MS system as well as a second MIRA Ultra analyser (S/N 100775) agree well for both accuracy and temporal variability (Figure 33, middle, bottom). Data demonstrate the advantages of high-resolution data by laser spectroscopy over hourly measurements with GC-MS to capture the actual variability of C_2H_6 in ambient air. Analysis of CH_4 and co-emitted tracer by one analyser waives the need to correct time lags and variable instrumental response functions.

Figure 33: Temporal trends of CH_4 and C_2H_6 concentrations in ambient obtained from the MIRA Ultra analyser and a Picarro CRDS (model 2401) (top), a GC-MS system (middle) as well as a second MIRA Ultra analyser (S/N 100775) (bottom).

8.4 Conclusions

Established tracer gases SF_6 and SF_5CF_3 are well established for agricultural studies as they offer low and stable concentrations in background air, no natural sources and sensitive (ppt) analytics (GC-ECD). Their use, however, is criticized for having a high environmental footprint (GWP) in particular when used with less sensitive analytics / high dosing.

Ethan and ethine were evaluated as potential replacements, with lower environmental impact and the capability for on-line analytics at ambient concentrations. Commercial analytics (Aeris MIRA Ultra) for C_2H_6 / CH_4 were purchased and demonstrated sufficient precision but require regular calibration for drift correction. When calibrated appropriately instruments demonstrated accuracy by inter-comparison measurements with CRDS (CH_4) and GC-MS and second Aeris MIRA Ultra analyser (C_2H_6).

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